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Correction: Measuring social response to different journalistic techniques on Facebook

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Correction to: *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0507-3>, published online 01 July 2020.

The original version of the paper included a spelling mistake in the author information.

The incorrect spelling read:

Fabina Zollo

The correct spelling now reads:

Fabiana Zollo

This has been corrected in both the online and PDF article file.

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